

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGABO****FIRST NAME: FRANCIS****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 02%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Starting the essay (EUCLID 2024, 7)
2. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2024, 8-9)
3. Writing the Essay (EUCLID 2024, 10-11)
4. Rules of thumb to write a paper (EUCLID 2024, 12- 14)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Euclid University offers programs to different groups of people, some of them with the need to be acquainted with the fundamentals of professional and academic paper writing. The coursepack of period one provides the foundation for academic writing in the form of guidance, best practices, and dos and don'ts.

The coursepack aims at equipping the students with the basic tools to write an appropriate essay that meets academic standards. It is packaged in such a way that it can be used as a handbook for academic writing consultation. Its topics range from advice on how to collect and organize information and grammatical structure to an example of a corrected paper.

I was interested in all the chapters of coursepack, but for the purpose of the Response Paper One of the course ACA-401D, I selected the following five concepts to discuss starting the essay, researching the topic, writing the essay, rules of thumb to write a paper and the style guide.

2) FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

The fundamentals of essay writing touch on all steps involved in the writing, starting from putting together ideas until the essay is drafted and proofread. A good essay starts with proper planning and information gathering with a combination of appropriate styles. It is worth noting that the coursepack also offers the instructor's perspective in assessing the essay (EUCLID 2024, 3).

a) Starting the Essay

A good academic essay starts with proper planning. The coursepack provides key advice that might look obvious yet very fundamental for a good academic essay. Issues like procrastination, lack of proper question definitions, or inappropriate planning are some of the challenges affecting academic essays.

I personally liked the pyramid, which shows the basic steps in essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 8). It is a good tool for those who are not properly acquainted with academic writing. For an engineer like me who did not have opportunities to write many academic papers, the advice on how to organize initial thoughts or conduct research around key questions will improve my writing skills.

The advice from the coursepack is practical for drafting all kinds of papers. I will use this advice as one of the guiding principles for drafting my papers throughout this program. However, we should supplement this guidance with other readings on how to write a good essay, especially for students aspiring to publish in academic journals.

b) Research the Topic

In all the steps of essay writing, I think that the most important one is the research about the topic. This is where one acquires knowledge and substance to develop the topic of the essay. The depth and shallowness of the essay will depend on how systematically the topic was researched.

It is good to research a topic, but adopting a systematic approach while doing so is essential. The coursepack gives good suggestions on how to keep focus while researching the topic. I personally concur with the proposed questions to keep focus on the topic while conducting the research (EUCLID 2024, 8), especially when the topic is broad and multi-disciplinary.

The guidance on critical and creative thinking is key in the preparation of essay writing. Unfortunately, it was not developed at length in this coursepack, as in other paragraphs therein. I hope that in the subsequent periods of the course, I will be exposed to this important topic. Otherwise, students will have to explore this important skill.

3) WRITING THE ESSAY

Writing is the culmination phase of the essay. It is where all information gathered during the research is developed in line with the topic. The writing approach proposed in the coursepack is crucial as it can be applied to different types of papers with an emphasis specifically on an essay.

The skills to move from the generic to specific in the introduction with the right questions and answers and develop the body of the essay without diverting from the topic are important for successful writing. To maintain a logical flow of ideas and arguments throughout the draft, Dr Jeunese Adrienne Payne advises keeping the planning iterative (Payne 2012, 2).

I found practical advice to ‘Keep the essay’ question in mind’ (EUCLID 2024, 11). This is more relevant in the era of the Internet, where there is countless documentation on almost any topic. One can easily lose focus on the topic or divert from it because of the abundance of material to research from the Internet. Therefore, it is important to keep the bearing of the topic's question while drafting and editing.

4) RULES OF THUMB TO WRITE A PAPER

These are other useful suggestions for a successful essay since effective writing requires a combination of skills, topic knowledge, and a mixture of common sense. My understanding of these rules is that they were compiled out of years of experience as they speak to key areas to focus on or mistakes to avoid.

This part of the coursepack reiterates again the importance of staying focused while drafting the essay, especially on the part advising to confine oneself to the aspects that are of immediate relevance (EUCLID 2024, 13). However, I am of the view that this has to be taken in the right context as some of the topics that are multi-disciplinary in nature, like climate change, need to be analyzed from different angles.

The advice of writing clearly and avoiding making the essay boring or clumsy is key, though not straightforward. It requires a great deal of common sense and a good understanding of who the paper intends to be. One can argue that a boring paper for one reader can be interesting to another. Therefore, I believe that there is a certain level of subjectivity when assessing whether the essay is boring, clumsy, or not. However, I think that this kind of skill will come with experience and proper guidance from the lecturers throughout the program.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Mastering a specific writing style can be an indicator of a good writer. This is especially important for students embarking on a PhD program since their papers will need

to meet a certain academic standard and go through processes of review. While noting that EUCLID has adopted the Chicago Rules, students should be familiarized with other major writing styles as well in preparation for eventual future opportunities that require other styles.

A handbook of the style required by the university, the university, or a customer should be kept at hand for consultation at almost all stages while writing. Though some aspects of the style, like font, manuscript layout, use of headings, or paragraph numbering, might become familiar after a few writings, we should be aware that different customers or papers might call for different style requirements.

As the coursepack puts it rightly, the style guide is a necessary tool if some elements of a paper or essay need to be kept consistent (EUCLID 2024, 41). As students who need input and contributions from different people for our academic papers, we need to master the writing styles, especially those prescribed by the EUCLID University.

6) **CONCLUSION**

The coursepack is the perfect subject to start with in an academic program because it lays the foundation of academic writing. The guidelines and advice proposed in it provide a good handbook that can accompany the student throughout the program at the university.

The topics in the coursepack are developed in a way to initiate the student to proper essay writing and prepare for upcoming courses. Apart from the concepts discussed in this response paper, the coursepack contains other useful topics for effective academic writing.

I was encouraged to read the whole document and have decided to consult it throughout my program and supplement it with other documents related to academic writing. Unlike the grammatical structure that clearly indicates the dos and don'ts in an academic paper, some of the skills prescribed in the coursepack would be acquired through experience and continuous guidance of lecturers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Jeunese Adrienne Payne. 2012. "Essay Writing Handout". Accessed on August 15, 2024. <https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/teaching/1718/SWSecEng/essay-cst1a-2018.pdf>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.